

Transcription of Interview 7

November 2020

Shane: Hello Mrs Interview 7.

Mrs Interview 7: Good morning, Shane.

Shane: Good morning. I'm sorry for all the trouble, I'm glad we managed to get through to each other.

Mrs Interview 7: Yes.

Shane: So my interview just consists of four questions, so it shouldn't take too much of your time; but it's, largely, just around your personal experience and perceptions and working with the National Health Insurance. So my first question, rather broadly, is, what is your view of the National Health Insurance?

Mrs Interview 7: Okay. My view on this National Health Insurance, I think this is a good initiative, that was [...] to healthcare services for all South Africans, especially those that are disadvantaged and cannot access some of the healthcare services that they need to access. But also, this will depend on the sustainability on the funding of this [...].

Shane: And when you say, regards to the findings of the system, what aspects are you referring to?

Mrs Interview 7: I'm referring to money being available. Yes, I know that there are some billions that have been, probably, demarked for this [...], but with our current.. for an example, current economic status to this covid-19, of which we don't know when and how are we going to recover; so this is going to be.. how is the government going to be able to fund the system; that's what I'm trying to say.

Shane: Okay. And with regards to the funding, what do you think of the current funding strategy, that's proposed by government?

Mrs Interview 7: I don't have a problem, as such, though, we might not get back our [...], if we only do.. if they go that route; and also, the thing of, maybe, trying to [...] and [...] what they are trying to [...]. But what can I say, because the government has decided they will implement what they have decided to do.

Shane: Okay. And they speak about a strategic purchasing, where there is a separation of the funder, who is the purchaser, such as the body that would purchase from the provider, that would be both public and private sector. What do you think of that sort of system?

Mrs Interview 7: No, that system, to me, I don't see anything wrong with that system, myself.

Shane: Okay. And the capitation, or the per capita payment, that they model, do you have any views on that?

Mrs Interview 7: No, I have no views on that one.

Shane: And your views on working together with the private sector, do you see it as positive, negative, mixed?

Mrs Interview 7: It's positive, it's positive. Ja, it's positive, because I think that [...] for the South Africans.

[05:11]

Shane: Okay. Why is it that you say that?

Mrs Interview 7: I'm saying that, because, currently, if you look at the private sector and their facilities, compare it to our public sector facilities, they are sort of like more compliant, in as far as the national [...] are concerned, and in as far as the resources are concerned. So if we have this alliance and then working together with them, I think we can have a system, whereby, when we don't have particular [...] service that can [...], we are, maybe, able to transfer that patient to a private hospital, without any hassles.

Shane: Okay. And with regards to your own engagement in NHI policy development, have you been engaged with the process?

Mrs Interview 7: I once attended the roadshow that the health department was doing, and also tried to go through the policies. But what I see, is that the role of a medical aid fund, has been overlooked, maybe under used, due to the fact that they will only be expected to sort of like top up for services that the NHI funding is not covering for patients or clients. And then, also, on the issue of governance on a private healthcare facilities, because now they will now be expected to function, more or less, like us in the public and lose on their profits. And also, part of the issue of private facilities being selected to partake in this universal health coverage. Remember now, it's not going to be all facilities engaging or participating, or meeting the criteria, to be funded. So it will still be creating some [...] in our communities, and having more patients, now blocking in the facilities that will be funded [...].

Shane: Okay. And the news that you have received around the NHI, is that something that you've, for instance, attended meetings or roadshows, or has there been direct communication from government?

Mrs Interview 7: No, there has been some communication through them sending us their policies and the [...]; and then, yes, also through these roadshows; that's where we gained more insight into this.

Shane: Okay. And your perception around the implementation of the National Health Insurance, its current implementation, as well as moving forward?

Mrs Interview 7: Ja, I think, as I said, remember, due to this [...] now, the government has announced that there won't be any salary increment, and there won't be any increment in our compensation of employees budgets.

[10:11]

Shane: Yes.

Mrs Interview 7: Because one of the requirements for these, is to ensure that facilities are adequately staffed. So if, now, we have this situation where we can't hire more than what we have, currently, but we will only be replacing those that are leaving, and looking at the current situation of the shortage of staff, I don't think that that will give us a positive outcome, so far. That's my take. And also, on the issue of some of the infrastructure in some of the facilities, remember, some of our facilities are houses, hence, so now we have this current economic status that we are in, I think it's going to be tough one for the government to implement, in terms of try and meet these pilots.

Shane: Alright. So you mention human resources and infrastructure, as two big challenges to this NHI rollout; are there any other that you can see?

Mrs Interview 7: Ja, it is that, because of any challenges regarding medication or supplies, so ja, we don't have that a big problem. And also, big mistakes in our facilities, currently, in trying to reach their ideal standards, or ideal hospitals standards, because, ja, you'll find that it's very, very difficult, if a facility has reached its criteria.. the next time you go and assess that facility, it loses the status again, because, ja, probably something that was maybe today, it's not there, because of the system, or maybe not getting things that you want.

Shane: Okay. And with regards to the readiness of the public health service, what are your views on that?

Mrs Interview 7: I don't think we are ready.

Shane: Okay.

Mrs Interview 7: I don't think we are ready. We still have a lot to do, for these changes.. because, as I've said, that we will have our facilities meeting the criteria for an ideal clinic, but after some few weeks or months down the line, if you go back to that facility, as I'm saying, that you might find that what was there, when the facility was assessed before its assessment day, they don't have it at that time. So I don't think we are ready.

Shane: What do you think it would take for us to get ready to implement the NHI?

Mrs Interview 7: I think it's consistency in maintaining our facilities; consistency in procurement of consumer products that are required; and then also, consistency in ensuring that we have enough adequate categories of staff, that are needed, for all the facilities.

Shane: Okay. And from the manager's perspective, do you feel empowered, or engaged enough, to bring about these changes?

Mrs Interview 7: It's inbetween and betwixt, in the era of covid, because they want us to be engaged.. Okay, we know what is supposed to be done, but the challenge, is managing it to move towards the goal that the department has set. And as I'm saying, that it is one step at a time. But I believe with all those challenges economically, definitely problems in rolling it out.

[15:37]

Shane: So you would say, a large factor in its success, is the overall economic welfare?

Mrs Interview 7: [...] and [...] think the economy is in a good state, that also impacts on the social status of the people on the ground, because more people will be working, and ja, that will also be improving on their working as a community. But if we have an economic state, whereby people are losing jobs and who are unemployed, then that also affects their social status, and they will be having more worries, more depression, and then, I mean, the facility will see big numbers.

Shane: Yes. And the overseeing management, do you regard it as appropriate, as is? Or is there any adjustments that you would make to the managerial system, for implementation?

Mrs Interview 7: I think what is more important, is that the health system needs to be strengthened, it's communication.

Shane: Okay.

Mrs Interview 7: That's very important. Communication, engagement with all the stakeholders, [...], I think that's the big key that needs, for me, that can make things better. Because if we communicate, we keep people knowing on what is expected of them, their plans and also their changes, and trying, and then trying to make them dive into all the changes that the government wants. That's very important for us, as management.

Shane: Okay. Okay, Mrs Interview 7, that's all the questions that I have from my side; is there any other view or thought that you would like to express?

Mrs Interview 7: Not as such, but my view is that, if this system is implemented and is successful, I think we will have a better South Africa.

Shane: Okay then, Mrs Interview 7, thanks so much for your time; I know it was difficult to squeeze me in, but I really appreciate it. And then once I've gotten the interview transcribed into word document, I'll just send it through to you, if you would like to review it, or make any amendments.

Mrs Interview 7: Okay, nice, okay.

Shane: Okay. Thanks again for your time.

Mrs Interview 7: Okay, bye, thank you.

Shane: Bye.

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